

Lab protocols to study Solute Carrier Transporters

A combinatorial CRISPR/Cas9 KO screen to test genetic interactions between Solute Carriers

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12819677

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Protocol description

The Solute Carrier (SLC) family is characterized by a high level of substrate redundancy which may diminish phenotypes in regular KO models since lost SLC functions can be compensated by other family members. A systematic screen for genetic interactions, i.e., when the combinatorial KO of two genes shows a stronger phenotype than the added individual KOs, is therefore crucial to reveal otherwise hidden loss-of-function phenotypes.

This protocol describes our effort to use a recently developed combinatorial CRISPR Cas9 KO system to test all possible pairwise interactions for all 258 SLCs that are expressed (>1 transcript per million) in the human colon cancer cell line HCT116. The library for this project contained around 400.000 gRNA combinations. Cell numbers and reactions can be scaled up or down if needed to adapt the protocol for comparable genetic interaction screens.

Materials

Biological materials:	<p>General materials:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ 293T packaging cells▪ pMD2.G (Addgene #12259), psPax2 (Addgene #12260) packaging constructs▪ Cas9 expressing HCT116 clone (e.g., HCT116-Cas9-p2A-Blast-c1, RESOLUTE #CE06MZ-1) <p>Optional materials (for library cloning):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Cas9 gRNA expression vector pWRS_1001 (Addgene #192205)▪ Oligo library (recommended: Twist bioscience)▪ Endura Electrocompetent cells and recovery medium <p>Optional (for generation of Cas9 expressing cell line):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ lentiCas9-Blast (Addgene #52962) or similar construct
Reagents:	<p>General reagents:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Q5 Polymerase (NEB) or self-purified Pfu-Sso7d Polymerase (Wang et al. 2004) (with Phusion HF buffer, NEB #B0518S)▪ AmpliClean™ Cleanup Kit (NimaGen, SKU: AP-050) <p>Optional (for library cloning):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Esp3I (NEB)▪ T7 DNA Ligase (NEB)▪ BSA (10 mg/ml) (NEB)▪ Dithiothreitol (DTT)
Equipment:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ 10-stack tissue culture dishes (Corning, #3270)▪ Electroporation equipment (optional for custom library)▪ CASY cell counter

Procedure

Step 1: Library cloning (skip step if using ready-made library)

1.1 Cas9 gRNA design

We recommend selecting 4-6 gRNAs per gene for combinatorial CRISPR KO screens. In this case, we designed 6 gRNAs per gene using the VBC score algorithm (1). As controls, we chose 12 gRNAs targeting 12 different olfactory receptors (ORs). For the cloning strategy outlined below, the gRNA sequences need to contain the initial G nucleotide that serves as transcriptional start site.

Note: If restriction enzyme digestion with PacI and XbaI is planned for library amplification (Step 3.3), avoid gRNAs that contain these restriction sites.

1.2 Oligo design for pooled synthesis

Depending on the desired library, oligos can be synthesized in two ways:

Option 1: order oligos containing both gRNAs:

This option allows flexibility in which gRNAs should be combined since each oligo is designed and synthesized individually:

5'- FW primer-CGTCTCGCACC-gRNA1-GTTTCAGTCTTCCGGCGAAGACACCTGAAAC-gRNA2 (reverse-complement)-GGGAAGAGACG-RV primer (reverse-complement) -3'

Option 2: order FW and RV oligos with one gRNA each

In this option all gRNAs on the FW oligos will be recombined with all gRNAs on the RV oligos through the common linker sequence (GTTTCAGTCTTCTAATTTCTACTGTCGTAGAT) that is present in both FW and RV oligos. However, using different primer sequences for different subsets of oligos allows specific PCR amplification of a subset of gRNA combinations. E.g., we divided the 258 target SLCs into four subgroups and chose four distinct FW oligo primers for each of them. FW oligos with control gRNAs targeting 12 olfactory receptors were designed with all four FW primer sequences. The RV oligos (SLCs and olfactory receptors) all contain the same primer sequence. This strategy allows the amplification of four sub-libraries in four separate PCR reactions, each containing a subset of SLC gRNAs on the 1. gRNA position combined with all other SLCs on the 2. gRNA position.

FW oligo: 5'-FW primer-CGTCTCGCACC-gRNA1-GTTTCAGTCTTCTAATTTCTACTGTCGTAGAT -3'

RV oligo: 5'-RV primer (reverse-complement)-CGTCTCTTCCC-gRNA2-GTTTCAGGTGTCTTCATCTACGACAGTAGAAATTA -3'

Alternatively, if unique gRNAs in each gRNA pair are preferred (gene1-gRNA_1-gene2_gRNA_1, gene1-gRNA_2-gene2_gRNA_2, gene1-gRNA_3-gene2_gRNA_3, etc.), oligos can be designed so each gRNA group (e.g., 1-6) is synthesized with sequences for distinct primer pairs (FW_primer1_gRNA_1 + RV_primer1_gRNA_1, FW_primer2_gRNA_2, RV_primer2_gRNA_2, etc.). That way, each amplified sub-library will only contain one combined gRNA pair from one gRNA group. After amplification, sub-libraries can be mixed at equimolar ratios or clones separately and mixed before virus production.

Examples for FW and RV primer for oligo amplification:

Primer group	FW primer	RV primer	Ta (Q5 Pol)
1	AGGCACTTGCTCGTACGACG	ATGTGGGCCCGGCACCTTAA	71
2	CCCGGTTGCTAACAAAAGCA	GAGGTTGTGATCGCTGAGGT	67
3	AGCGGAAACCCCAACAGTTA	AGGGTCAGTAGAACATGCGT	67
4	GCAATCCCGATGGCACCATG	TTCCCACGGAGTCCCTTGTC	70
5	GTGTAACCCGTAGGGCACCT	GTCGAGAGCAGTCCTTCGAC	69
6	GAGACCATTGCGAATACCAG	AGAAGGCCGTAGTCAGTTAC	64

1.3 Amplify ssDNA oligos by PCR:

Option 1: (library oligos containing both gRNAs ordered)

1xMM	
Q5 buffer	10 µl
NTPs (10 mM)	1 µl
Q5 Pol	0.5 µl
oligo amplification primer (10 µM)	2.5 µl
Cas9 oligos (0.5 ng/µl)	5 ng
H2O	to 47.5 µl

- Set up PCR amplification reaction:

Step1: 98°C for 30 sec

Step2: use recommended annealing temperature as shown above for 30 sec

Step3: 72°C for 15 sec

Repeat Step2-3 for 12-16 cycles

Keep at 4°C

Option 2: (library ordered as FW and RV oligos with one gRNA each)

- Set up strand extension reaction:

6xMM	
Q5 buffer	60 µl
NTPs (10 mM)	6 µl
Q5 Pol	3 µl
Mixed Cas9 oligos FW/RV	20-30 ng
H2O	to 285 µl

- Divide MM to 6 x 47.5 µl in PCR tubes.

- Run program in thermocycler:

Step1: 98°C for 30 sec

Step2: 98°C for 10 sec

Step3: 55°C for 30 sec

Step4: 72°C for 10 sec

Repeat Step2-4 for 5 cycles

Cool down to 4°C

- Add 2.5 µl oligo amplification primer pairs (10 µM) to each PCR tube
- Run PCR amplification program:

Step1: 98°C for 30 sec

Step2: use recommended annealing temperature as shown above

Step3: 72°C for 15 sec

Repeat Step2-3 for 20-25 cycles

Keep at 4°C

1.4 Purify PCR products magnetic DNA purification beads as described in the manufacturers protocol:

- Gently shake AmpliClean beads to resuspend the magnetic particles to obtain a homogeneous suspension.
- Add 1.8 x volume of AmpliClean to the PCR product (e.g., 90 µl beads to 50 µl PCR).
- Mix thoroughly by gentle vortexing and incubate for 3 - 5 minutes at room temperature.
- Place the reaction plate onto the Magnetic Ring Plate for 2 minutes.
- While sitting on the magnet, remove the cleared solution from the reaction plate and discard by pipetting from the center of the bottom of the wells. Make sure the removed solution is fully cleared and do not remove any magnetic particles.
- While leaving the plate on the magnet, immediately dispense 150 µL of 70% ethanol to each well of the reaction plate and incubate for 30 seconds at room temperature.
- Remove the ethanol and discard. Repeat this step and make sure to completely remove all Ethanol with the last aspiration.
- Optional: Dry for max. 5 minutes at RT. Take plate from the magnet.
- While plate is off the magnet, add 25 µL of elution buffer to each well of the reaction plate and homogenize the beads in the elution buffer by pipetting up and down.
- Place the reaction plate onto the magnet plate for 1 minute to separate beads from the solution and transfer the eluant, containing the purified PCR products to a new plate.
- Measure concentration of purified PCR product using Qbit HS assay.
- Run 10 µl of purified PCR product on gel to check product size (expected: ~150 bp).

1.5 Set up golden gate reaction:

Compound	µl
Amplified Cas9 oligos	200 ng
pWRS_1001	2 µg
2 x T7 Ligase buffer	34 µl
Esp3I	5,4 µl
T7 Ligase	2.7 µl
DTT	0.7 µl
BSA (10 mg/ml)	0.7 µl
H2O	to 68 µl

Note: Volumes and concentrations can be scaled up or down if necessary

- Incubate reaction in thermocycler:
 - Step1: 37°C ... 5 minutes
 - Step2: 20°C... 5 minutes
 - Step3: 37°C... 5 minutes
 - Repeat Step2 and 3 for 40 cycles
 - Keep at 4°C
- Purify golden gate reaction with 1 x volume AmpliClean beads as described above.
- Elute in 30 µl H₂O or EB buffer.
- Digest reaction with 1 µl Esp3I or BsmBI in 1 x Cutsmart buffer (NEB) to reduce uncut/re-ligated background at 37°C for 2-3 hours.
- Purify golden gate reaction with 1 x volume AmpliClean beads as described above.
- Elute in 8 µl H₂O.

1.6 Transformation of plasmid library

Transformation is carried out in a 0.1 cm gap cuvette using 25 µL of Endura Electrocompetent Cells. Optimal settings for electroporation are listed in the table below. Typical time constants are 3.5 to 4.5 msec.

Electroporation Settings:

- 1.0 mm cuvette
- 25 µF
- 200 Ohms
- 1500 Volts

Suggested Electroporation Systems:

Bio-Rad Micro Pulser #165-2100; Bio-Rad E. coli Pulser #165-2102; Bio-Rad Gene Pulser II #165-2105; BTX ECM630 Electroporation System; Eppendorf Electroporator 2510. Optional transformation control reactions include electroporation with 1 µL (10 pg) of supercoiled pUC19 DNA.

- Have Recovery Medium and 17 mm x 100 mm sterile culture tubes readily available at room temperature (one tube for each transformation reaction).
- Place electroporation cuvettes (0.1 cm gap) and microcentrifuge tubes on ice (one cuvette and one microfuge tube for each transformation reaction).
- Remove cells from the -80 °C freezer and place on wet ice until they thaw completely (10-20 minutes).
- When cells are thawed, mix them by tapping gently. Aliquot 2 x 25 µL of cells to the chilled microcentrifuge tubes on ice.
- Add 2 x 2.5 µl of purified golden gate reaction to each tube with 25 µl cells and mix by gently tapping the tube several times. Avoid air bubbles when pipetting.
- Carefully pipet 2 x 25 µL of the cell/DNA mixture into chilled electroporation cuvettes without introducing bubbles. Quickly flick the cuvette downward with your wrist to deposit the cells across the bottom of the well. Electroporate according to the conditions recommended above.
- Within 10 seconds of the pulse, add 975 µL of Recovery Medium to the cuvette and pipet up and down three times to resuspend the cells. Transfer the cells and Recovery Medium to a culture tube.

- Place the tube in a shaking incubator at 250 rpm for 1 hour at 37 °C and combine 2 x 1 ml afterwards.
- Spread 1 µl of undiluted and 1 µl of 1:10 diluted cells on agar plates with carbenicillin.
- Inoculate 250 ml ONCs with remaining cells (~2 ml).
- Incubate the plates overnight at 37°C.
- Incubate 250 ml ONCs at 30°C overnight (preferably only 12-14 hours)
- After overnight incubation, count colonies on 0.1 µl plates and calculate total number of clones in ONC by 20.000.
- Usually, at least 50-fold coverage of the CRISPR library is recommended to achieve good representation of all gRNA combinations. Therefore, if the library contains 160.000 oligos, the 0.1 µl plate should contain at least 400 colonies.
- If coverage is substantially lower than 50x, repeat transformation with more competent cells.

1.7 Purify plasmid library and check quality.

- Harvest bacteria from 250 ml ONC and purify plasmid using Maxiprep kit (Qiagen).
- Measure plasmid concentration using nanodrop device.
- Send plasmid library for Sanger sequencing with hU6-f primer (GAGGGCCTATTTCCCATGATT) to Microsynth or another sequencing provider. Expect a sequence with double peaks at both gRNA sites that flank the linker sequence. If gRNAs of varying lengths have been designed, expect double peaks at the second gRNA position.
- Pick 8-12 colonies from 0.1 µl plate and incubate 5 ml ONCs at 37°C.
- Next day, purify plasmids with a miniprep kit and sequence with hU6-f primer. >90% of plasmids should contain two gRNAs from the library.

1.8 Insert VCR1-WCR3 tracrRNA sequence between gRNAs

VCR1-WCR3 tracrRNA sequence:

GAAGACCG|GTTT|AAGAGCTATGCTGGAAACAGCATAGCAAGTTTAAATAAGGCTAGTCCGTTATCAACTTTG
CTGGAAACAGCAAAGTGGCACCGAGTCGGTGCTTTTTTGAACCGACGGATGATCTCGTGCACCGGTTCAAAAA
AGCACCCGACTCGGGTGCCACTTTTTCAAGTTGTAAACGGACTAGCCTTATTTCAACTTGCTATGCACTCTTGT
GCTTAGCT|CTGA|AAGTCTTC

Underlined: BbsI recognition sites

|| BbsI cut sites

Red: VCR1 tracrRNA

Blue WCR3 tracrRNA

Note: The VCR1-WCR3 sequence can be synthesized as dsDNA fragment (e.g. from Twist Bioscience) but due to relatively high error rate in the synthesis it is recommended to order the fragment with cloning overhangs, subclone it, verify sequence identify, and purify the sequence in 10-12 cycles using a high-fidelity Polymerase (e.g. Q5 from NEB).

Set up second golden gate reaction:

Compound	μ l
VCR1-WCR3 tracrRNA (dsDNA)	200 ng
pWRS_1001 library with gRNAs	2 μ g
2 x T7 Ligase buffer	34 μ l
BbsI	5,4 μ l
T7 Ligase	2.7 μ l
DTT	0.7 μ l
BSA (10 mg/ml)	0.7 μ l
H2O	to 68 μ l

Note: Volumes and concentrations can be scaled up or down if necessary

- Incubate reaction in thermocycler:
 - Step1: 37°C ... 5 minutes
 - Step2: 20°C.... 5 minutes
 - Step3: 37°C.... 5 minutes
 - Repeat Step2 and 3 for 40 cycles
 - Keep at 4°C
- Purify golden gate reaction with 1 x volume AmpliClean beads as described above.
- Elute in 8 μ l H2O.

Transform Endura competent cells with final library and purify plasmid as described above (1.6-1.7).

Step 2: Transduction and cell culture

2.1 Generate a Cas9 expressing clone (skip if Cas9 expressing clone is already available)

- Generate lentiviral particles using lentiCas9-Blast (Addgene #52962) or a similar Cas9 expressing vector instead of the library as described below (virus preparation).
- Transduce cell line of interest with lentiviral particles and select with appropriate concentration of blasticidin (to be tested for each cell line).
- Sort single cell clones from selected cell pool (by FACS or serial dilution) and expand clones.
- Test Cas9 activity of expanded clones using e.g. combinatorial gRNAs against two surface markers CD46 and CD81.
- You should reach at least 80% double KO efficiency in a clone before moving on to perform pooled genetic screens.

2.2 Virus preparation

Day 1:

- Seed (in the afternoon) 9×10^6 HEK 293T cells per plate in 2 x 15 cm plates (1x15 cm plate will yield 50 ml of supernatant with viral particles).

Day 2:

- Prepare transfection mix:

Component (per 15 cm plate)	µg	µl
Serum free medium		888
pMD2.G	5.83	
psPax2	8.74	
Cas9 gRNA library	11.7	
PEI (stock: 1 mg/ml)		145
DMEM (w/o Pen/Strep)		2300

- Start the transfection in the morning.
- Mix the plasmids in the serum free medium.
- Add the PEI and vortex for 10 s, spin down if too much liquid stays on the side of the tube.
- Incubate for 15 min at RT.
- During the incubation, add 17 ml of fresh medium (w/o Pen/Strep) to the cells.
- Gently add medium (without Pen/Strep!) to the transfection mix and pipet up and down slowly 2x.
- Add dropwise 3.2 ml of the transfection mix per plate.
- Gently swirl the plate to distribute the mix.
- In the afternoon (7-8 hours after transfection): replace medium with 25 ml fresh harvest medium (without Pen/Strep!).

Day 3:

- In the afternoon, collect the virus medium from the plates in a falcon tube and store in the fridge.
- Add 25 ml fresh medium to the plates.

Day 4:

- In the afternoon, collect the virus medium from the plates and mix with the medium from the previous day.
- Filter the medium with a 0.45 µm filter.
- Freeze the medium at -80°C (freeze a few stocks in 1.5 ml tubes for titration).

2.3 Virus titration

Day 1:

- Seed 15.000 HCT116-Cas9-p2A-Blast-c1 cells/well in a 9-well plate, use medium without Pen/Strep.

Day 2:

- Thaw a virus stock from the -80° at RT.
- Add increasing amounts of virus to the cells (see below).
- Add Protamine Sulfate to each well (stock 8 mg/ml, final dilution: 1.3 µg/ml)

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Dilution factor	200	100	50	30	20	10	5	3	ctrl 1	ctrl 2	
A	PBS	PBS										PBS
B		1.0	2.0	4.0	6.7	10.0	20.0	40.0	66.7	0	0	
C		1.0	2.0	4.0	6.7	10.0	20.0	40.0	66.7	0	0	
D		1.0	2.0	4.0	6.7	10.0	20.0	40.0	66.7	0	0	
E												
F												
G												
H		PBS										

Day 3:

- Transfer cells to 24-well plate in the morning, add selection medium (1 µg/ml Puromycin) in the afternoon.

Day 5 onwards:

- Wait until the selection control is dead (ctrl 1).
- If the no-selection control (ctrl 2) is confluent, transfer to a larger plate.
- Once the selection control is dead, quantify the percentage of live cells via Cell Titer Glow.
- Recommended: also count the cells with a cell counter as a control.
- For easy to transduce cell lines, a 1:100 dilution of the virus usually results in an MOI of ~0.3. If titer is significantly below, more viral particles need to be generated and possibly concentrated before transduction.

2.4 Transduction and selection

Day 1:

- Seed 400 million HCT116-Cas9-p2A-Blast-c1cells per 10-Layer stack.

Day 2:

- Replace medium with fresh medium (no Pen/Strep).
- Add virus at a dilution that resulted in an MOI of around 0.3 in the titration assay.
- Add 1.3 µg/ml protamine sulfate.

Day 3:

- Passage cells and re-seed 400 million cells per 10-Layer stack, also seed 9 million cells on 15 cm dishes to be able to observe them under the microscope.

In the afternoon, add puromycin to a final concentration of 1 µg/ml.

2.5 Passaging and cell harvesting

Materials needed per 10-Layer stack:

- 1.5 L RPMI (10% FBS, 1% P/S)
- 500 ml PBS
- 200 ml Trypsin

- A sterile plastic bottle with a capacity of >200 ml
- 3-7x 50 ml falcon tubes
- 2x15 ml falcon tubes
- CASY tube
- 10 ml CASYton
- Autoclaved glass bottles (total capacity needed: ~2.5 L)

General notes:

- Passage the cells 2 times per week:
 - For a 3-day incubation period, seed 250 million cells
 - For a 4-day incubation period, seed 220 million cells
- Once per week, collect 2x220 million cells per pool and freeze at -80°C.
- To distribute liquids equally across all layers:
 - Close both lids of the stack.
 - Turn the stack onto its' long side and wait for the liquid to level out on all layers.
 - Turn the stack onto its' short side, away from the lids and then put the stack the right way up again.

Passaging:

- Pour medium from the 10-Layer stack into an autoclaved glass bottle.
- Wash with 250 ml PBS.
- Add 200 ml Trypsin.
- Incubate for 5 minutes.
- Once the cells have detached from the plate, pour them into a sterile bottle.
- Add 250 ml PBS to the stack to wash out cell clumps, leave the PBS while you are preparing the cells to avoid drying out any remaining cell clumps.
- Pour 200 ml medium into a second sterile bottle.
- Transfer 10 ml of the cells in trypsin into a 50 ml falcon tube, pipette up and down multiple times to loosen up any cell clumps, then transfer the cells to the bottle with medium.
- Once all cells have been transferred, transfer 1 ml to a safe-lock tube.
- Add 25 µl of the cell suspension to 10 ml of CASYton in a CASY tube.
- Count the cells using programme 19 on the CASY.
- Multiply the cell count by 4 and calculate the needed volume for reseeding the cells.
- Transfer the volume of cells to a bottle of fresh RPMI.
- Pour out the PBS from the 10-Layer stack, then pour the cell suspension into the stack.
- Add a total of 1.5 L RPMI to the stack.

Cell harvesting:

- Transfer 2x220 million cells to 50 ml falcon tubes.
- Centrifuge the cells at 300 g for 5 min.
- Remove the supernatant.
- Resuspend cell pellets in 2x10 ml PBS and transfer to 15 ml falcon tubes.

- Centrifuge the cells at 300 g for 5 min.

Resuspend the cells in 5 ml PBS with 20% DMSO then freeze at -80°C.

Step 3: gDNA purification

Materials needed:

- Qiagen genomic tips: 100/G (for up to 4×10^7 cells per sample) or 500/G (for up to 2×10^8 cells per sample)
- Qiagen Genomic DNA Buffer Set: C1, G2, QBT, QF and QC (can also be prepared in the lab)
- RNase A (100 mg/ml) (Qiagen)
- Proteinase K (20 mg/ml)
- TE buffer [pH 8.0]
- Optional: PacI enzyme (20 μ l per sample)

3.1 Prepare cell nuclei for purification:

- Use freshly harvested cells or thaw frozen cells on ice.
- Follow manufacturers protocol:
- Thaw frozen cells on ice and add 5 ml PBS.
- Centrifuge cells at 1500 x g for 10 min at 4°C.
- Remove supernatant and resuspend cells in 10 ml cold PBS. Divide cell suspension to 2 x 5 ml in 2 x 50 ml tubes. Add 5 ml cold PBS to each tube for a total of 10 ml volume.
- Add 10 ml ice cold buffer C1 and 30 ml ice cold distilled water to each 50 ml tube. Incubate on ice for 10 min.
- Centrifuge cells at 1300 x g for 15 min at 4°C (preferably in a swing-out rotor).
- Discard the supernatant and resuspend nuclei with 2 ml ice cold buffer C1 and 6 ml ice cold distilled water.
- Centrifuge cells at 1300 x g for 15 min at 4°C.
- Remove supernatant (leave around 300-500 μ l volume behind). And freeze nuclei at -80°C.

3.2 Purify gDNA from nuclei:

Genomic tips can be re-used to purify gDNA from another 1×10^8 cells from the same sample (equilibrate with buffer QBT after elution before next purification).

- Thaw one of the two tubes of each sample (1×10^8 cells).
- Resuspend nuclei in left-over volume of C1/H₂O volume (300-500 μ l) by vortexing at max. speed.
- Add 10 ml buffer G2 rapidly and pipet up and down a few times immediately to avoid precipitation. Vortex 10-30 sec. at max. speed.
- Add 20 μ l RNase A (100 mg/ml) to samples and mix by vortexing.

- Add 200 µl Proteinase K (20 mg/ml) to sample, mix by short vortexing and incubate at 50°C for 60 minutes.

Note: Incubation time may be extended if precipitates are still visible after 60 minutes. Sonication might aid to dissolve precipitates but leads to significant DNA degradation.

- Equilibrate a QIAGEN Genomic-tip 500/G with 10 ml of Buffer QBT and allow the QIAGEN Genomic-tip to empty by gravity flow.
- Vortex the sample for 10 s at maximum speed and apply it to the equilibrated QIAGEN Genomic-tip. Allow it to enter the resin by gravity flow.

Note: While the sample is flowing through column, start preparing the second tubes with nuclei for all samples (as above).

- Wash the QIAGEN Genomic-tip 2 x 15 ml of Buffer QC.
- Elute the genomic DNA with 1 x 15 ml of Buffer QF.
- Equilibrate used tip with 10 ml of Buffer QBT and apply other half of sample (1×10^8 cells). Repeat steps as before. In parallel, continue with DNA precipitation of first half of sample:
- Add 10.5 ml (0.7 volumes) room temperature (15–25°C) isopropanol to the eluted DNA and precipitate the DNA by mixing vigorously and centrifuging immediately at $>5000 \times g$ for at least 15 min at 4°C. Carefully remove the supernatant.
- Wash the centrifuged DNA pellet with 4 ml of cold 70% ethanol. Vortex briefly and centrifuge at $>5000 \times g$ for 10 min at 4°C. Carefully remove the supernatant without disturbing the pellet. Air-dry for 5–10 minutes and resuspend the DNA in buffer.
- Dissolve the DNA in 750 µl TE buffer [pH 8.0] overnight on a shaker or at 55°C for 1–2 h. Resuspend the DNA pellet by rinsing the walls to recover the DNA.
- After elution of second half of sample, combine resuspended DNA (2 x 750 µl).
- Measure concentration of DNA sample. A total of 1200 µg of gDNA should be yielded to achieve full coverage for sequencing.

Note: If columns get clogged, a syringe with adapter can be used to apply pressure and assist flow-through.

3.3 (Optional): PacI/XbaI digestion (if restriction sites are absent in gRNAs)

The pWRS_1001 vector contains PacI and XbaI restriction sites that can be used to digest gDNA with inserted gRNA sequences to improve the efficiency of the subsequent amplification of the gRNA sites by PCR.

- Set up PacI/XbaI digestion (1800 µl volume):
 - 1500 µl gDNA (1200 µg)
 - 180 µl 10xCutSmart buffer
 - 10 µl PacI
 - 10 µl XbaI
 - 100 µl H₂O
- Digest at 37°C for 48 hours.
- Inactivate enzymes at 65°C for 20 minutes.

Digested gDNA can be used for PCR without further purification but total volume of PCR should be >5 -times larger than digested gDNA volume to avoid buffer interference.

Step 4: Amplify combinatorial gRNAs for Illumina sequencing.

4.1 Primer sequences

Staggered FW primer sequences:

```
pWRS1001_F1  ACTCTTTCCCTACACGACGCTCTTCCGATCTTGTGGAAAGGACGAAACACC
pWRS1001_F2  ACTCTTTCCCTACACGACGCTCTTCCGATCTCTGTGGAAAGGACGAAACACC
pWRS1001_F3  ACTCTTTCCCTACACGACGCTCTTCCGATCTAATGTGGAAAGGACGAAACACC
pWRS1001_F4  ACTCTTTCCCTACACGACGCTCTTCCGATCTGCATGTGGAAAGGACGAAACACC
pWRS1001_F5  ACTCTTTCCCTACACGACGCTCTTCCGATCTCGACTGTGGAAAGGACGAAACACC
pWRS1001_F6  ACTCTTTCCCTACACGACGCTCTTCCGATCTTCGACTGTGGAAAGGACGAAACACC
pWRS1001_F7  ACTCTTTCCCTACACGACGCTCTTCCGATCTATCCACTGTGGAAAGGACGAAACACC
pWRS1001_F8  ACTCTTTCCCTACACGACGCTCTTCCGATCTGACACCCTGTGGAAAGGACGAAACACC
```

Staggered RV primer sequences:

```
pWRS1001_R1  ACTGGAGTTCAGACGTGTGCTCTTCCGATCTAGTTCTGTATGAGACCACTC
pWRS1001_R2  ACTGGAGTTCAGACGTGTGCTCTTCCGATCTTAGTTCTGTATGAGACCACTC
pWRS1001_R3  ACTGGAGTTCAGACGTGTGCTCTTCCGATCTCTAGTTCTGTATGAGACCACTC
pWRS1001_R4  ACTGGAGTTCAGACGTGTGCTCTTCCGATCTGCTAGTTCTGTATGAGACCACTC
pWRS1001_R5  ACTGGAGTTCAGACGTGTGCTCTTCCGATCTCGACAGTTCTGTATGAGACCACTC
pWRS1001_R6  ACTGGAGTTCAGACGTGTGCTCTTCCGATCTTCGGAAGTTCTGTATGAGACCACTC
pWRS1001_R7  ACTGGAGTTCAGACGTGTGCTCTTCCGATCTATCCGGAGTTCTGTATGAGACCACTC
pWRS1001_R8  ACTGGAGTTCAGACGTGTGCTCTTCCGATCTGACACCCAGTTCTGTATGAGACCACTC
```

Note: Use combinations of all staggered FW and RV sequences for your samples to ensure good colour balance for Illumina sequencing (e.g., F1+R1, F2+R2, , F8+R8).

4.2 Set up PCR reactions to amplify combinatorial gRNAs

Set up test PCR to check template and PCR conditions:

	µl
5X Q5 buffer or Phusion HF buffer	10
10 µM primer (F/R)	2.5
NTPs (10 mM)	1
Q5 Pol or Pfu-Sso7d Polymerase	0.5
H2O	x
5 µg gDNA template	x
Total	50

- Run PCR program:
Step1: 98°C for 1 min
Step2: 98°C for 10 sec
Step3: 60°C (Pfu-Sso7d) or 61°C (Q5) for 30 sec
Step4: 72°C for 30 sec

Repeat Step2-4 for 5 cycles

Step5: 98°C for 10 sec

Step6: 72°C for 1 min

Repeat Step 5-6 for 19-22 cycles

Step7: 72°C for 2 min

Keep at 4°C

- Run PCR (10 µl) on agarose gel (expected PCR product size: 360-380 bp).
- If strong but not overamplified PCR (additional larger sized bands indicating "PCR bubbles" product, scale up PCRs and run tested program. E.g., for 1200 µg gDNA Input, set up 12000 µl PCR reaction and divide into 96 x 120 µl PCRs (expect some volume loss during pipetting) on a PCR plate.
- After PCR completion, combine 10 µl of each 120 µl PCR in a 1.5 ml tube.
- To generate plasmid libraries for sequencing (input controls): use 1-10 ng plasmid library as template per replicate, run program as above for 5 (61°C annealing) +10-15 (72°C annealing) cycles. Purify PCR product with 1,3 x volume AmpliClean beads as described above (no double size-selection required).

4.3 Double-size selection of pooled PCR products

- Gently shake the AmpliClean to resuspend the magnetic particles to obtain a homogeneous suspension.
- Add 0.6 x volume of AmpliClean to PCR product (e.g., 60 µl when using 100 µl of the pooled PCRs).
- Mix thoroughly by pipetting up and down and incubate for 3 - 5 minutes at room temperature.
- Place the reaction plate onto the Magnetic Ring Plate for 2 minutes or until solution becomes clear).
- While sitting on the magnet, transfer the cleared solution into new tube (this solution contains the unbound PCR product while large gDNA fragments are bound to beads).
- Add another 0.6 x (original) volume (e.g., 60 µl when 100 µl PCR were used) to the ~160 µl cleared solution.
- Mix thoroughly by pipetting up and down and incubate for 3 - 5 minutes at room temperature.
- While sitting on the magnet, remove the cleared solution from the reaction plate and discard by pipetting from the centre of the bottom of the wells. Make sure the removed solution is fully cleared and do not remove any magnetic particles.
- While leaving the plate on the magnet, immediately dispense 500 µL of 70% ethanol to each well of the reaction plate and incubate for 30 seconds at room temperature.
- Remove the ethanol and discard. Repeat this step and make sure to completely remove all Ethanol with the last aspiration.
- Optional: Dry for max. 5 minutes at RT. Take plate from the magnet.
- While plate is off the magnet, add 25µL of elution buffer to each well of the reaction plate and homogenize the beads in the elution buffer by pipetting up and down.
- Place the reaction plate onto the magnet plate for 1 minute to separate beads from the solution and transfer the eluant, containing the purified PCR products to a new plate.

- Measure concentration of purified PCR product using Qbit HS assay.
- Run 10 µl of purified PCR product on gel to check product size and purity.

4.4 Set up barcoding PCRs

- Barcoding primer:

i7 primer: CAAGCAGAAGACGGCATAACGAGAT (i7 index) GTGACTGGAGTTCAGACGTGTGCTCTTCCGATCT

i5 primer: AATGATACGGCGACCACCGAGATCTACAC (i5 index) ACACTCTTTCCCTACACGACGCTCTTCCGATCT

Barcodes for barcoding primer:

barcode	seq	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
i7-D01	CGAGTAAT	C	G	A	G	T	A	A	T
i7-D02	TCTCCGGA	T	C	T	C	C	G	G	A
i7-D03	AATGAGCG	A	A	T	G	A	G	C	G
i7-D04	GGAATCTC	G	G	A	A	T	C	T	C
i7-D05	TTCTGAAT	T	T	C	T	G	A	A	T
i7-D06	ACGAATTC	A	C	G	A	A	T	T	C
i7-D07	AGCTTCAG	A	G	C	T	T	C	A	G
i7-D08	GCGCATT	G	C	G	C	A	T	T	A
i7-D09	CATAGCCG	C	A	T	A	G	C	C	G
i7-D10	TTCGCGGA	T	T	C	G	C	G	G	A
i7-D11	GCGCGAGA	G	C	G	C	G	A	G	A
i7-D12	CTATCGCT	C	T	A	T	C	G	C	T
i5-D01	AGGCTATA	A	G	G	C	T	A	T	A
i5-D02	GCCTCTAT	G	C	C	T	C	T	A	T
i5-D03	AGGATAGG	A	G	G	A	T	A	G	G
i5-D04	TCAGAGCC	T	C	A	G	A	G	C	C
i5-D05	CTTCGCCT	C	T	T	C	G	C	C	T
i5-D06	TAAGATTA	T	A	A	G	A	T	T	A
i5-D07	ACGTCCTG	A	C	G	T	C	C	T	G
i5-D08	GTCAGTAC	G	T	C	A	G	T	A	C

- Plan combinations of indexing primer for samples that should be multiplexed for Illumina sequencing to ensure good colour balance (C/A vs G/T). E.g., for 8 samples: use i7-D01 to i7-D08 together with any i5 primer (i7 indices are enough for demultiplexing). If more than 12, e.g. 16 samples are multiplexed, use i7-D01 to i7-D08 together with i5-D01 and i5-D02 or i7-D01 to i7-D04 together with i5-D01 and i5-D04 to achieve 16 unique index combinations with good colour balance for both indices.

- Prepare MM (per 25 µl PCR):

Q5 buffer: 5 µl
 NTPs: 0.5 µl
 Q5 Pol: 0.25 µl

Water: 14.75 µl

20.5 µl MM + 2 µl purified PCR from Step 4.3 + 2.5 µl 5 µM i5/i7 barcoding primer mix.

- Run PCRs for 8-10 cycles at standard NEB Q5 program with 72°C annealing temperature.
- Expected amplicon size after barcoding PCR: 434-454 bp.
- Purify barcoded libraries with 1.2 x vol. magnetic beads and elute with 25 µl EB buffer.
- Run aliquots of PCRs on gel (~8 µl) and measure concentration with Qbit.

4.5 Multiplex libraries for Illumina sequencing

- Measure concentrations of purified barcoding PCRs using a Qbit DNA quantification system or a similar device.
- Multiplex libraries at equal amounts according to the measured concentration.
- The final multiplexed sample should contain at least 100 ng DNA at a concentration of >5 ng/µl. Exact requirements should be discussed with the corresponding sequencing facility.

Step 5: Library sequencing

5.1 Library sequencing

- The final Illumina library contains the following elements:

```
AATGATACGGCGACCACCGAGATCTACAC-i5index-ACACTCTTTCCCTACACGACGCTCTTCCGATCT
-stagger-TGTGGAAAGGACGAAACACC-gRNA1-
GTTTAAGAGCTATGCTGGAAACAGCATAGCAAGTTTAAATAAGGCTAGTCCGTTATCAACTTTGCTGGAAACAGCAAAGTG
GCACCGAGTCGGTGCTTTTTTGAACCGACGGATGATCTCGTGCACCGTTCAAAAAAGCACCCGACTCGGGTGCCACTTTT
TCAAGTTGTAACGGACTAGCCTTATTTCACCTGCTATGCACTCTTGTGCTTAGCTCTGAAAC-gRNA2(rc)-
GGGAAAGAGTGGTCTCATAACAAGACT-stagger-AGATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTCAC-i7index-
ATCTCGTATGCCGTCTTCTGCTTG
```

Underlined: PCR FW/RV primer sequence

Red: VCR1 tracrRNA

Blue WCR3 tracrRNA

- Choose sequencing platform to yield at least as many reads per sample to match read number to the number of clones in the stably transduced cell pool. E.g., when a library with 4×10^5 oligos was transduced into 8×10^8 cells at an MOI of 0.5 to reach 4×10^8 transduced clones at a 1000-fold coverage, aim for a minimum of 5×10^8 reads (considering that the read mapping rate is usually only 75-80%) per sample.
- Use 5% PhiX spike-in to improve colour balance.
- Sequence library in 2 x 100 bp paired-end mode with dual indexing to cover both gRNA sequences and parts of the VCR1-WCR3 sequences.

5.2 Data processing

- Check read quality using [FastQC](#), also freely available (no local installation required) on the Galaxy platform (3).
- Trim reads using cutadapt to remove common flanking sequences and stagger:
Read1 (contains gRNA1):

1. Cutadapt with 5'adapter: TGTGGAAAGGACGAAACACC
Max error rate: 0.1
Min overlap: 15

2. Cutadapt with 3'adapter: GTTTAAGAGC
Max error rate: 0.0
Min overlap: 10

Read2 (contains gRNA2):

1. Cutadapt with 5'adapter: TATGAGACCACTCTTTCCC
Max error rate: 0.1
Min overlap: 15

2. Cutadapt with 3'adapter: GTTTCAGAGC
Max error rate: 0.0
Min overlap: 10

- Use FASTQ joiner to combine FW and RV reads (gRNA1-gRNA2).
- Generate a tabular file with three columns that contains all gRNA combinations in the used library:
Column1: unique oligo name
Column2: unique oligo sequence (gRNA1-gRNA2)
Column3: gene ID (gene-gene pair name), identical for all oligos targeting these two genes
- Use MAGeCK count tool (4) or custom script to map reads in fastq format to oligos. MAGeCK tools are also available on the Galaxy platform (3).
- The output tables contain raw and normalized read counts for each oligo.

Additional notes

Sections of this protocol were copied from manuals for reagents and kits as provided by the manufacturers. Some steps were modified to adapt to our workflow and should not be regarded as general recommendations for these reagents.

Data availability

Data from the SLC super family wide combinatorial CRISPR/enCas9 KO screen will be made available shortly at the [RESOLUTE database](#).

References

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